

First record of the crab spider *Diaea rohani* Fage, 1923 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

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ABSTRACT

The crab spider *Diaea rohani* Fage, 1923 was previously known only from Angola. It has now been recorded from South Africa, extending its current distribution range in Africa from Angola to South Africa. This species is possibly undercollected and is suspected to occur in more countries. The general morphology of the species is discussed and photographs of live specimens provided. Notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa and conservation are provided.

Key words: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), taxonomy

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Diaea* Thorell (1869) is represented by 46 species and nine are known from Africa (World Spider Catalogue, 2022). During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), surveys were undertaken throughout the country (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) and large numbers of thomisids have been sampled. The species *Diaea rohani* Fage, 1923 previously known only from Angola has been recorded for the first time from South Africa.

The general morphology of the male is discussed based on live specimens. Notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa and conservation are provided.

METHODS

The voucher specimens sampled during SANSa surveys are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida of the Agricultural Research Council Plant Health and Protection division. SANSa made requests for photographs of spiders for the SANSa Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012), and several photographs of the species were received from the public.

TAXONOMY

Diaea rohani Fage, 1923

Diaea rohani Fage, 1923 224; Fage, 1925: 194; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2022: 24.

Diagnostic characteristics: *Diaea rohani* is a small to medium-sized spider, known only from the male (Figs 1–3 & 9). Male: total length 4–5 mm. Carapace varies from fawn to pale green, with two narrow brown lateral bands stretching from the posterior lateral eyes to near to the posterior edge; eye area white; carapace with scattered long setae. Abdomen white, decorated with a broad median pale brown band almost covering dorsal area with two white lateral irregular bands covering about two-thirds the length and four to five black spots (Figs 7–8); dorsum with numerous strong setae. Legs fawn, similar to carapace; only two anterior legs with half of tibiae, metatarsi and tarsi dark; legs with numerous scattered setae especially on femora. Palp with long retrolateral apophysis with tip curved (Figs 4–6).

Juvenile: In an immature female (Fig. 10) the carapace was a pale green without bands; abdomen same as male; legs pale green.

Figures 1–3. *Diaea rohani*: 1 & 2. Male from Wakefield farm. Photo credits: Peter Webb.

Figures 4–8. *Diaea rohani*: 4–6. Male palp. 7–8. Male habitus. Photo credits: 4 & 7. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman. 5, 6, 8. After Fage (1925).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Angola and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Eastern Cape: Maclear (-31.08, 28.35). **Free State:** Zastron farm Opnek (-30.29, 27.09). **Gauteng:** KwaMhlanga (-25.42, 28.70). **Kwa-Zulu-Natal:** Wakefield farm near Howick (-29.26, 29.56); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83). **Western Cape:** Aardvark Nature Reserve (-33.494, 21.088).

Figures 9–10. *Diaea rohani*: 9. Male from Kloof. 10. Immature female from Aardvark Nature Reserve. Photo credits: Peter Webb.

BEHAVIOUR

They are free-living plant-dwelling spiders that are more commonly found on shrubs and herbs. They were sampled with sweeping and beating of the vegetation from the Fynbos, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Grassland Biomes.

CONSERVATION

From South Africa the species is recorded from five provinces and it is protected in Aardvark Nature Reserve. Although the female still need to be described, the species has a wide range and no threats are known it is listed as Least Concern.

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